

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

InterLied: Toolkit for Computational Music Analysis

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Supervisor: Rafael Caro Repetto

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Dedication

I would like to dedicate this work to Jan. Thank you for everything.

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Abstract

InterLied is an interface, run by a set of algorithms for music score (primarily lieder) analysis. The project is musicologically motivated, thus it streams towards wider accessibility. It not only consists of the algorithms for music (pattern) analysis, but also provides the informative jupyter notebook and a case study that serves as a tutorial for less computationally experienced users. In order to make the codes more accessible, the project also allows the user to run the algorithms through the interface (GUI), a convenient format for users with little computational knowledge. The latter allows the user to apply the algorithms to their corpora without direct interaction with the code. The algorithms' primary focus is a "music pattern" – melodic, rhythmic, and textual (e.g., lyric), but they also explore metadata information. While music parameters, such as key, meters and other musical features are being studied with music21 Python library, the patterns and lyrics are analysed with methods from computational linguistics, such as n-grams and word tokenization. Aside from thorough explanation of the benefits of the algorithms, this thesis also focuses on limitations of computationally applied methods, addresses their disadvantages and problematises the current issues of digital humanities. Both, advantages and disadvantages of applied computational approach are being explored through two case studies, demonstrated on 63 Slovenian 20th century lieder ("art" songs) by three composers - Marij Kogoj, Slavko Osterc and Lucijan Marija Škerjanc, first focusing on musical features alone, and second including lyrics and metadata information.

Keywords: python, algorithmic musicology; music21; NLP; music patterns

Chapter 1

Introduction

Digital humanities have found themselves in an interesting but also challenging era. On one side, the digital humanities, with digitisation and by that, the preservation of archival materials, have nowadays already a rather firm position in a wider social context. On the other hand, these processes have and still are uncovering a series of difficulties, some of which are tackled better than the others. Even if we, for a moment, set aside what a challenge it is for a humanities researcher to utilise all possible digital tools, let alone to be able to adapt them to the specific needs of individual research, as Johanna Drucker implied,

the humanities are not a mere afterthought, simply studying and critiquing the effects of computational methods. Humanistic theory can provide ways of thinking differently, otherwise, specific to the problems and precepts of interpretative knowing — partial, situated, enunciative, subjective, and performative. Our challenge is to take up these theoretical principles and engage them in the production of methods, ways of doing our work on an appropriate foundation. The question is not, Does digital humanities need theory? but rather, How will digital scholarship be humanistic without it? [1]

But then again, how can IT and humanities fields cooperate when the wheels of

computational tools, algorithms and other processes are that incomprehensible for the latter?

If we address the digital musicology, which is the central concern of this thesis, there are many projects that try to include the musicologist (or any other humanities specialist) into the process of computation. From “Transforming Musicology” [2] to “The Baudelaire Project” [3] and then again to music21 [4] and “Partitura 0.4.0” [5], the projects are extending their goals past either musicological or IT scholarly world, but focus on addressing a wider interdisciplinary audience. These projects are in no doubt an immense contribution towards interdisciplinary collaborations between the “two” fields, first two addressing the users through creative topic-focused interfaces and the other two offering numerous tools for digital musical data and metadata information. Both groups, however, lack one minor thing - they are either very, although rightfully limited to a single topic, or hard to utilise without having a clear idea of how programming functions.

The general motivation of this project is therefore to contribute to a better communication between the fields and provide a bridge from one, humanities side to the other, IT field and vice versa. InterLied¹ is an assembly of open source tools for researchers with different levels of technical proficiency. It primarily focuses on lieder analysis, but it can also be applied to various musical forms and genres. The main advantage, aside from the algorithms themselves, of this project is the accessibility, meaning it is the user’s choice on how they wish to apply the offered functions, based on their level of computational proficiency. Hence, the InterLied package includes the scripts and informative notebook with pre-set execution commands, but is also designed as an interface, assuring the researchers with the least to none experience to have an undisturbed experience. The latter, being designed as a GUI, is still requiring some, but very minor amount of guided interaction with the code, as both (pre-set) requirements installation and the interface have to be executed from prompt command / terminal with two separate commands. This approach, I believe, encourages the user to enter the world of computation, while the “musi-

¹Repository can be accessed through here: <https://github.com/vnborsan/interlied>

cologically” explained algorithms promote the presence of humanities in the world of computation. In the end, InterLied as opposed to many other projects, allows the user to work with their own database instead of only exploring the pre-loaded information.

In the following chapters, the thesis will first introduce many other contributions that facilitated the progress of digital humanities / digital musicology. Next chapter will focus on a detailed explanation of InterLied’s construction - the computational functions for music analysis, which explore music patterns through relative values of Western Symbolic Music Notation, lyrics, and metadata. Afterwards, the case study will follow, introducing and then exploring Slovenian 20th century lieder with InterLied’s tools. The study will take on two different general research questions about the same corpus and dissect them by utilising the offered algorithms. By this approach, I will provide a tutorial on how to begin with utilising the InterLied apparatus and indicate some of the possible types of researches one is able to undertake with the tools. In the final chapter, the discussion will dissect the advantages and limitations of not only the tools in question, but similar digital approaches in general.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

In this chapter we will observe the contributions made to the field of digital humanities and digital musicology. First section will focus on more or less algorithmic contributions that concern InterLied, while the second will provide some examples of accessibility of these tools (interfaces, digital archives etc.).

2.1 Music Patterns, Lyrics and Natural Language Processing

From the perspective of a Slovenian musicologist, Slovenian classical music has not yet been well explored with the utility of computational methods. However, pattern recognition in the widest sense is a very commonly researched topic in both, humanities, and natural, “hard” sciences. As Gilovich described, pattern recognition assists when making decisions and judgements as well as organising new information or knowledge [6]. Organising information through patterns help us deal with chaos and chance, and thus provide a certain level of stability and “security.” Thus, the vast frequency of pattern-motivated research contributions is not a surprise.

Melkonian, et. al., rightfully implied that “musical patterns are hard to define” [7]. We observe these from various perspectives, from symbolic to audio data, their relationships with listener’s or musician’s perception to, then again, composer’s in-

tents and so forth. Researching music patterns is therefore attracting many different scholarly fields. Among them, we can certainly list cognitive sciences, psychology, acoustics, and chiefly MIR and musicology. Out of the latter two, which perform as the most relevant referential fields for this research, it appears as the subject itself nowadays generally blossoms in world of IT expertise rather than (historical) musicology. Work on patterns in music itself has been explored by many established researchers, among them Anja Volk, who, while exploring music patterns in folk music, realised, “that melodic contour, rhythm, lyrics and motifs are important ingredients for the similarity between the songs” [8]. In her studies, she mainly focuses on (sequential) alignment algorithms, which have been, in her opinion, very successful for retrieving tune families, e.g., preserving only the “relevant” patterns of the scores in order to explore the most meaningful connections or similarities between the tunes [8, 9, 10]. Another approach was introduced by Erik Scerri, who explored pattern classes by automated pattern discovery with long short-term memory neural networks [11]. His work indicated that it is “possible to train an LSTM neural network on patterns combined synthetically in sequence that are taken from a realistic dataset and have the learned model be able to identify those patterns in their original scenarios,” but have as well confirmed the complexity and challenges of discovering music patterns [11]. Janssen et. al. [12] split music pattern research into two general groups - geometric [13, 14] and string-based, the latter of which could be further devised into methods with [15] and without indexing structure [16]. Consequently the field is nourishing more than one legitimate approach to this issue. The disparate nature of music pieces one intends to observe requires special individual treatment as well as particular research questions can benefit more from one technique than the other. Although the InterLied’s approach of n-grams (explained in detail in the next chapter) cannot claim the complexity level of many methods mentioned above, I believe, nonetheless, the explainability of the method allows for easy adaptations, especially when we consider the users with less computational experience, making it a very convenient instrument for musicologists and other primarily humanities and social sciences researchers.

When we talk about music exploration tools, many have been developed in the last

two decades, mostly dealing with audio, but also for investigating symbolic musical data. First in line is “music21” [4], a python package which can be found in many other analysis packages, including InterLied. Another two projects that partially run on music21 are ELVIS Project (VIS - Music Analysis Framework)” [17, 18] and “Partitura” [5], second of which is further explained below. Besides these, some other contributions have been made to this field of interest, for example “Computational Music Structure” [19] or “Melody Extraction from Polyphonic Music Signals using Pitch Contour Characteristics” [20] and “Music information retrieval: Recent developments and applications” [21]. Achievements from the pattern research is also well explained in “A Computational Evaluation of Musical Pattern Discovery Algorithms” [22]. More recently, in May of 2021, a new Python package was developed by Maarten Grachten, Silvan Peter and Carlos Cancino-Chacón, previously mentioned, Partitura. The principal aim of this project is, in their own words, “[...] to handle richly structured musical information as conveyed by modern staff music notation. It provides a much wider range of possibilities to deal with music than the more reductive (but very common) piano roll-oriented approach inspired by the MIDI standard,” but can also be used to represent both score-related and performance-related information [18].

The computational methods that are exploring music patterns, can often be found in interdisciplinary projects and are regularly, like this project, observing symbolic music data. If we, on the other hand, further observe the input to global algorithmic music research in general, the computational music research projects usually belong to the domain of computational sciences and mainly focus on audio data. Most of these music analysis algorithms are incomprehensible or very challenging to be independently used by musicologists. The tools seldom include the variety of aspects that a musicologist’s eye would notice or require. And, as the researcher of that sort can neither understand nor apply and modify the available models, it is very difficult for them to benefit from the developing computational techniques, let alone actively participate in the development process. From this follows, that musicologists need to be included in the process of computational analysis and consequently must be able to 1. understand, 2. utilise, so that they can 3. contribute.

First, Nicholas Cook must be given immense credit on generally encouraging the connections between computation and musicology. With some of his contributions mentioned in the following sections, I believe we must note his most exhausted work on interdisciplinarity in music studies, a book *Beyond the Score: Music as Performance* [23], where he, among other focuses involves computational music analysis as one of the essential means of music research. A good example of interdisciplinary collaborations is many of the already mentioned projects and SymPlot visualisation algorithm [24], however this contribution, like the ones noted above, once again did not provide a graspable analytical approach for musicologists and neither to this project. Here, we must note that many computational scientists also understand the importance of addressing the issue of “digital” music research, for which a notable example would be Xavier Serra’s discussion in which he exposes an ambition many digital music researchers share, and that is “to go beyond the study of individual artifacts and analyze the overall system of interconnected entities in order to model a musical culture as a whole” [25].

InterLied project believes, that the beginning of achieving such goal is to take a couple of steps “back” in order to introduce the computational dimensions to the musicologists. The InterLied’s analysis and exploration tools are therefore especially tailored to musicologists’ understanding.

The algorithms of this project are generally focusing on the “n-gram”, a technique born in the area of Natural Language Processing. There are some contributions that have already approached this issue, some of them being by Michael Fell *Natural language processing for music information retrieval: deep analysis of lyrics structure and content* [26] and “Lyrics Segmentation: Textual Macrostructure Detection using Convolutions” [27] another one by Kento Watanabe and Masataka Goto “Lyrics Information Processing: Analysis, Generation, and Applications” [28] and one large contribution by Steven Bird, Edward Loper and Ewan Klein “Natural Language Processing with Python” [29]. Fell explores how lyrics structures repeat and correlate with music structures, while Watanabe and Goto approach this topic on three different levels – lyrics analysis, lyrics generation and writing support, and lyrics-centred

applications. The latter, by Bird et. al. further dissects the broader application of NLP processes to python algorithms.

As InterLied in its beginnings still focuses on music, the NLP application is for the time being very minor. With utilising NLTK Python package [29], the lyric is appended to each entry, as well as tokenized and offers reduced token list per score, per pattern and per interval. The latter is applying a stopwords removal method, a first step into preparation for other NLP processes. The project thus did explore the dimensions of topic modeling and settled on applying Latent Dirichlet Allocation (ADL). While the basic algorithm exists, it is not yet included in the package. Hence, the data preparation and upper references mostly serve as a suggestion for further work with text data.

2.2 Music Interface

As mentioned, the InterLied also takes the shape of a music-related interface. There have been several projects that engaged in interactive representation of the historical sources, for example the First World War 100 by The National Archives [30]. Some others established connections between different museums, archives, and different institutions with general information, for instance Discover Archives by International Council on Archives, [31] and Archaeological Collections Areas Database and Map by Archaeology Data Service [32]. Music-wise a lot of different interactive interfaces have been created. One of the most prominent undertakings was without a doubt first Transforming Musicology, [2] and years later Unlocking Musicology: Digital Engagement for Digital Research project series by Kevin Page and others at the Oxford e-Research Centre, whose general purpose was to “take methods and analyses from musicologists and show that, because they were undertaken digitally, we can more easily make use of them beyond academia” [33]. While these projects introduced an interesting way of interacting with musical analyses information, Baudelaire Song Project on the other hand digitally connected songs from all over the world through one common denominator – Baudelaire in a well-designed, comprehensible way [3]. Although the main structure of these projects is “being interactive” we must not

neglect the first part, which is the transparent comprehensibility and accessibility of the analysis models that power these structures. Next to that, the interfaces all serve a very clear and closed purpose. While this approach serves the projects very well, InterLied would like to cover more different aspects of what this type of digital data storage could bring to the table.

Chapter 3

System Overview

The algorithms of this project are generally written in Python with the aid of music21 library, which provides technical foundation of analysis. They are focused on exploring music interval n-grams, a technique which can more frequently be found in Natural Language Processing. InterLied understands these music n-gram pattern to be the at least twice repeated n-grams ($n > 2$). The NLP methods are applied to melody (melodic intervals), rhythm (rhythmic values) and lyrics (lyric tokenization). As the method follows the n-gram logic, some patterns do tend to overlap. That is why the measures are added to the beginning and ending of the pattern, and it is, from there, up to the user to choose which patterns are relevant for their research. By searching through element (gram) frequency the algorithms also account for their relationship with, for example, lyrics, rhythm etc. Despite analysing several music features, melodic n-gram or pattern remains a central observational point. Each pattern consists of intervals sequences of different length in a vocal part of lied. To this, the algorithms also append rhythmic and lyric pattern, title, composer and lyricist, key, meter diversity, and other musical features connected to the piece and the pattern.

The collected data is stored in forms of musicXML, csv (temporary pandas data frame) and midi. These are introduced to the GUI users through various options. Although InterLied's interface is currently in a form of GUI, it deems to eventually

turn into a web interface, which will serve as a connecting point for different archives' materials stored in different places. At the time being, some dialogue has been started with two music(ological) institutions in Slovenia. The interface itself is meant to be used by numerous social different groups, such as music professionals, public, music schools and music researchers. The latter of which will be able to, through precise understanding of the wheels of InterLied's structure, eventually contribute to further development of the algorithms and establishment of the global database. The model is designed with a wish to eventually grow into a sustainable apparatus and does not intend to only exhaust its purpose on a single enclosed topic.

In this chapter, I will explain the building blocks of InterLied, starting with detailed description of the algorithms, and then dedicating a chapter to the accessibility of the tools, explaining further the two approaches - InterLied's notebook and GUI.

3.1 The InterLied Algorithms

The algorithms could be grouped into three sets. First, we have the three basic algorithms that serve for data preparation, separately focusing on melodic intervals, music patterns and lyrics. When the data is ready, we can consider the next two groups, first of which are being plots and other visualizations. These include matplotlib plots of various parameter combinations, but also visualize the desired parts of the score and can export these to the user(s computer as midi. The last set of algorithms allows the user to explore all of the acquired data through filtering the data and providing the information in text or refined pandas data frame formats. The only prerequisite file type to run all functions is at least one musicXML score. The rest of the file types, such as csv, or already mentioned mid and pandas data frame can be created from score by the three basic functions.

3.1.1 Data Preparation

Although the tools are made to read a variety of different musicXML files, it must be noted that non-organised and poorly prepared data will cause issues when applying any algorithm. This section will expose some of the most important steps we must

follow in order to prepare a good database, not only for InterLied's purpose but also for applying any other computational model to it.

First of all, all files should be converted to the most commonly used musicXML format. Sibelius original format, MEI and other formats are not readable by these tools. We must be careful when inserting multiple voices, lyric, articulation or any other symbols, correctly as the computer can only respond to the pre-assigned functions a user attributes to each signature.

When preparing metadata information, we must note that most of music notation software (Musescore, Finale, Sibelius) offers an option of filling out all different types of information about the score. When it is converted to musicXML (if one uses another format first), a user should always manually check if it converted the fields correctly. The InterLied can so far read the fields of composer, title, lyricist and lyric (but many others can easily be added, so it is advised to fill out as much information one can gather per score).

When it comes to InterLied's reading of the metadata, the algorithm is very flexible. If there are, for example, multiple composers, titles or lyricists, my method was to separate them by the following symbol [;] (e.g., Mozart; Beethoven). However, one can apply their own rules to this - but note that the method should be consistent throughout the entire process, as this will make it easier to adapt the algorithms. The parameter "year" always remains marked as "none" and requires a manual input. This parameter can, by its flexible nature, indicate various things for various types of researches (from the date of manuscript, first edition, the chosen edition, composer's date of birth etc.) and it may be confusing for it to be generalised. Each user is allowed to define this parameter as they please. A user can also change this information manually, when the csv output is received. InterLied is made for primarily reading of a first single voice part, and that is why the algorithms are pre-set to reading `music21.score.parts[0]`, where they expect a single voice music line (no chords, etc.) to be stored in the first part. If the user's music sheet presumably stores the single voice line in another part, this should be adjusted in the scripts by changing the number in the square bracket. A user can also analyse multiple lines

of a single score, by adapting the number of the part each time they run the script. Note again, that InterLied at this moment cannot analyse multiple voiced streams.

3.1.2 Basic Algorithms

A. Intervals

The function called `interlied_intervals` turns a MusicXML file to a pandas data frame that is purposefully saved to user's computer as csv. From each score, it extracts metadata information and information related to the music analysis. Algorithm only observes the first, assuming vocal, part (e.g., `music21.score.parts[0]`). With `music21` function of `music21.analysis.segmentByRests`, the algorithm ignores the relationships between two consecutive notes divided by breaks. From that, a complete interval sequence list is created within the loop for each composition. Each interval element includes the ascending (plus), descending (minus) or oblique (underscore) symbol, thus M-2 and M+2 is not considered to be the same interval. This is useful especially when trying to grasp the vocal contours, to observe the score's peaks and to explore lyrics semantics. Intervals are described by numbers from 1 to 8 (where 1 equals unison and 8 equals an octave) and have assigned their quality as follows,

- P(5) = Perfect (fifth)
- A(4) = Augmented (fourth)
- D(4) = Diminished (fourth)
- M(3) = Major (third)
- m(2) = minor (second)

The algorithm first defines the interval and appends the metadata information (e.g., title, composer, lyricist, and year) to each. If metadata information is missing from the score, the field is marked with "None". This can later be substituted or

filled in manually. All interval elements also come with the following music analysis parameters, mainly supported by music21 algorithms:

- Start and end measure of the interval.
- Rhythm values consist of a tuple of both rhythmic note values of the interval where the measure unit consists of a quarter note, for example, M+2 has two tones whose rhythmic values are 0.5 and 1.0, where 0.5 equals one eighth note and 1.0 equals one quarter note.
- Key is predicted with the implementation of the KS algorithm (`music21.score.analyze`).
- In addition to the most probable key, the function offers alternative keys, writing down the top three most feasible guesses, also supported by music21 algorithm.
- Voice range is computed between the lowest and highest note value in the vocal part (e.g., `music21.score.parts[0]`) and is expressed as an interval (for example, M9).
- Meter change confirms whether the score has a meter change by YES/NO, and
- Exact meter or meters are computed and written down afterwards, in format of dictionary as, for example $\frac{3}{4}$.
- The first method for lyrics extracts the ‘assembled lyrics’ per interval. This means that the system takes all words at least partially connected to each note of the interval to make the process of lyrics segmentation / exploration.
- Second method tokenizes the lyric words per interval.
- The last method removes any stopwords we have set in advance.
- The final parameter is the language of the lyric.

This algorithm is using nltk packages, so if the language is included in their repository a user can access it through inserting the desired language (as a string) to the second input. The first input of this algorithm expects a folder of musicXML files. As an output, it writes all the information presented above in both, csv file (see figure 1), which is saved to user's computer and pandas data frame, which can be further used in the code itself. The csv format allows manual analyses and manual corrections and can be a stand-alone starting point for further research.

interval	duration	measure_start	measure_end	title	composer	year	lyricist	score_key_s	alternative_key(s)	veloc_range	meter_change	meter(s)	lyric_string	lyric_tokens
0	m-2 (1.0, 0.5)	2	2	Če sončna se razpenja vam pota	Marij Kogoj	None	Elizabeta Kremžar	d minor	[g minor, f major, c major]	M10	NO	(3/4)	Če sončna	sončna
1	d-1 (0.5, 0.5)	2	3	Če sončna se razpenja vam pota	Marij Kogoj	None	Elizabeta Kremžar	d minor	[g minor, f major, c major]	M10	NO	(3/4)	Če sončna se razpenja vam	sončna razpenja
2	m-2 (0.5, 0.5)	3	3	Če sončna se razpenja vam pota	Marij Kogoj	None	Elizabeta Kremžar	d minor	[g minor, f major, c major]	M10	NO	(3/4)	se razpenja vam	razpenja
3	m-2 (0.5, 0.5)	3	3	Če sončna se razpenja vam pota	Marij Kogoj	None	Elizabeta Kremžar	d minor	[g minor, f major, c major]	M10	NO	(3/4)	se razpenja vam	razpenja
4	d-1 (0.5, 0.5)	3	3	Če sončna se razpenja vam pota	Marij Kogoj	None	Elizabeta Kremžar	d minor	[g minor, f major, c major]	M10	NO	(3/4)	se razpenja vam	razpenja
5	m-2 (0.5, 0.5)	3	3	Če sončna se razpenja vam pota	Marij Kogoj	None	Elizabeta Kremžar	d minor	[g minor, f major, c major]	M10	NO	(3/4)	se razpenja vam	razpenja
6	P-5 (0.5, 0.5)	3	3	Če sončna se razpenja vam pota	Marij Kogoj	None	Elizabeta Kremžar	d minor	[g minor, f major, c major]	M10	NO	(3/4)	se razpenja vam	razpenja
7	m+3 (0.5, 2.0)	3	4	Če sončna se razpenja vam pota	Marij Kogoj	None	Elizabeta Kremžar	d minor	[g minor, f major, c major]	M10	NO	(3/4)	se razpenja vam pota	razpenja pota
8	d-1 (2.0, 0.5)	4	4	Če sončna se razpenja vam pota	Marij Kogoj	None	Elizabeta Kremžar	d minor	[g minor, f major, c major]	M10	NO	(3/4)	pota	pota
9	m-2 (0.5, 0.5)	4	4	Če sončna se razpenja vam pota	Marij Kogoj	None	Elizabeta Kremžar	d minor	[g minor, f major, c major]	M10	NO	(3/4)	pota	pota
10	m+3 (0.5, 2.0)	4	5	Če sončna se razpenja vam pota	Marij Kogoj	None	Elizabeta Kremžar	d minor	[g minor, f major, c major]	M10	NO	(3/4)	pota veselje	pota veselje

Figure 1: Example of csv output

B. Patterns

The intervals data tables, produced by the first function, can serve as an input to the next function, called `interlied_pattern_analysis`. What this particular algorithm does is to compute all n-grams ($2 < n < 30$) or patterns from the interval sequence obtained through the `interlied_intervals` function. Some data is collected for the first of the two grams only, assuming the information will inevitably be identical for the next gram as well. This is true for the metadata (title, composer, lyricist), score key, alternative score key(s), score meter(s), score's voice range and lyric language. Start measure number is retrieved from the first note of the first gram, and end measure is retrieved from the last note of the last interval of selected pattern. The lyrics elements represent a gathered bundle of words from all grams. Additionally, the user is also offered the information about pattern length. Since pattern is considered to be a repeated event, the function erases all grams that are unique. The user is informed about the quantity of patterns that were excluded from consideration. The output is the same as in intervals data table, thus data frame written onto the user's computer as csv file, but also remains as a pandas data frame variable, that can be further referenced in the code.

C. Lyric

The `interlied_lyric` function includes less metadata and musical data, but rather focuses on preparing the lyric in whole per score. The first two functions only deliver short excerpts of the lyric or tokens connected to much smaller pieces (e.g., interval or repeated pattern), while this, on the other hand, prepares the lyric with an aid of nltk Python package. It first extracts the lyric from the musicXML score, then tokenizes it and in the end, removes the stopwords. The collection of the latter is already provided with the nltk package in many languages, among them English, Italian, French, Spanish, etc. For the purpose of my own research, I extended the provided list of words. The rest of the offered language lists remain unchanged. The extension was done especially for the purpose of my targeted corpus as I have noticed that the articulations and other text marks in the score occasionally find their way to the lyric transcription, thus I have removed words such as *rall*, *allegro*, *andante*, and so on. This issue has been duly noted and will be one of the priorities when upgrading the InterLied algorithms. For now, the smoothest solution for the user is to update the stopwords list with the articulation signatures in that appear in the corpus. A large amount of this has already been removed in Slovenian stopwords list, however, as some of the articulation signatures that have been chosen by the composers do not stick to the “traditional” ones (e.g., making up their own words, expressions specific to the language, longer descriptions, abbreviations of traditional expressions etc.), it is hard to make a preset list that would be completely bullet-proof for any corpus one may want to observe. The transcribed and processed text of three described types is accompanied by the data about the lyricist, composer, and tonality, but can easily be extended should the user require more information. The inputs of this algorithm are first, a folder of musicXML scores and second, the chosen language. The outputs are a pandas dataframe and five text strings, providing some statistical information about the corpus. As the other two functions, this one stores a csv file to the user’s computer as well.

3.1.3 Plots and Other Visualisations

In this sub-chapter, I will introduce the visualisations InterLied offers. There are two categories of data representation, first the plots and second, the score and midi

representation.

There are four types of plots. First, `interlied_pitch_plot` realises the music21 score plot in the form of piano roll and pitch representation. It requires a single musicXML score to run and returns two colourful plots, which can be, as any other plots in this sub-chapter, downloaded onto the user's computer. As the music21 presents a larger issue to be incorporated into the interface, this plot is for now only accessible through the notebook.

Second, `interlied_top_10_plot` accepts any type of csv and a query, which should be the name of one column in the chosen csv. The algorithm returns a plot of ten most frequently fully repeated elements in that query and csv.

Third, `interlied_word_freq_q_plot` takes one csv (or directly the pandas data frame if we slightly modify the code) and two queries. Its pre-set function accepts a type of interval (e.g., M+3) as the query 1 and a score's title as query 2. Based on the user's input it delivers a plot of word frequency of all tokens that appear in the combination with the queries. Mind that this code is very easily modified and can explore word tokens through other parameters as well, replacing the 'interval' and 'title' with desired alternatives.

Lastly, `interlied_lyric_freq_plot` also explores the lyric, but instead of the pattern or an interval, utilises the lyric data frame. It takes one csv file in which it plots the frequency of words for chosen first key in chosen column 1 and chosen second key in chosen column 2, for example Franz Schubert in composer column plus C major in key/tonality column. The visualisation of the score is somewhat unreliable when done in Jupyter notebook. It does not mean it delivers wrong note values; however, the actual measure numbers can get lost or be misplaced alongside the other information (as articulation and other marks). Nonetheless, it serves its general purpose of rapidly visualising the data the user is interested in.

This is done by `interlied_view_midi_and_score`, which also delivers a midi excerpt of the same visualised piece. As an input, the user inserts the path to score, start and end measure. This function is supported by any software that

can (re)produce musicXML format, but the preferred program must be set in the music21 package. If the user does not wish to interact with music21 code, the algorithms will automatically run it on a free software called MuseScore 2.0 (unless a new version will update this feature), which needs to be downloaded beforehand. The function can run on any software that accepts musicXML formats, but this has to be pre-set in the music21. This InterLied's algorithm is much more efficient in the interface as it opens the excerpt directly in the software, where a user can correct the possible faults, save it to their computer, plays and saves the midi etc.

The `interlied_save_midi` option, which allows the user to download the midi file, is thus only available in Jupyter notebook.

3.1.4 Corpus Exploration

This category of algorithms helps the user to further explore their acquired data or the pre-composed database that comes with the InterLied package. For more experienced programmers, these can be modified or rewritten, as they only provide a glimpse of what exploring data with Python can offer. These are also incorporated into the interface, although due to GUI's performance, several functions may have a somewhat different structure from the ones offered in the notebook.

Many of them explore the connections between lyric and music parameters, first of which is `interlied_int_explore_lyric`. It requires a data frame acquired by the `interlied_intervals` function and returns a dictionary (e.g., info text) with the most common intervals and lyric words combinations in explored score. From this, we can explore in detail each instance where the interval and a specific word co-exist. This can be delivered by `interlied_int_explore_lyric_token`, which requires the data frame of the user's choice, composer's name, lyric token entry and interval entry. It returns a text with all information about these instances (from music parameters to metadata). We can notice that the data frame also requires composer information. This was added, assuming we may want to explore the same combinations within different corpora, or we have several composers stored in the same data frame. With slight modification this function can return a query of any

desired parameters' combination (for example replacing the composer for the lyricist, interval for rhythm pattern etc.). One of the modifications for this code is already included with the package, `interlied_search_pattern_lyric_composer`, which replaces the interval for pattern search, leaving the rest of the code the same. The last pre-set algorithm `interlied_search_melody_rhythm_composer` explores the relationship between rhythmic and melodic patterns, replacing the lyric parameter with the rhythm. It returns all instances of the score where both patterns match. While the functions above deal with data from either intervals or patterns data, the last explore option concerns itself with the `interlied_lyric` output. It returns a list of most frequent words per score, alongside score's title, composer, lyricist, and key.

3.2 Accessibility

InterLied is run by a completely open source algorithms. The project is copyrighted under the Creative Commons license, while the codes hold a GNU General Public License. When we discuss the difficulty-wise accessibility, the notebook is appropriate for users who wish to observe and or make changes to the code. It consists of the index that either guides the user to the code or to the explanation of all algorithms, mentioned in the previous chapter. All algorithms have comments and already provide the (commented) cell to run it. The pre-chapter of the notebook includes all dependencies imports and commented package installations if the user prefers to download them directly through the notebook. Chapter one introduces the three basic functions, chapter two plots and visualisations and chapter three focuses on the exploration algorithms. Below the code, there is an additional section which only includes all commands to run the code, referencing each individual algorithm. At the end of the notebook there are detailed descriptions of the algorithms which are hyperlinked with the top index as well as with the code cells.

3.2.1 Python Scripts and Jupyter Notebook

Python scripts are done separately for the purpose of the two different systems, jupyter notebook (or any other python code reader/executor) and separate for the GUI. For the purposes of introducing the first, let us focus on the scripts that run in the notebook.

The scripts are split into groups as follows:

- a. `interlied_basics_1.py`: Includes the function that runs the interval analysis.
- b. `interlied_basics_2.py`: Includes the functions that run pattern and lyric analyses.
- c. `interlied_exploration.py`: Includes the set of codes for corpus exploration.
- d. `interlied_visualisations.py`: Includes the set of codes for graphical data representation.
- e. `interlied_midiscore.py`: Includes functions that visualise score, midi and save midi to the user's computer.
- f. `interlied_stopwords.py`: Includes the function for defining and removing stopwords from textual data.

All functions are pre-defined in the included notebook, where the user can find short instruction and algorithm descriptions. A user can run scripts with only inserting the required parameters to each algorithm without interacting with any script, can copy the scripts into the notebook and modifies them or can make changes to the scripts directly and reloads them to the notebook.

3.2.2 The InterLied GUI

The InterLied interface is designed as an open source GUI in Python. All the codes that can be found in Jupyter notebook (except saving midi, see chapter 2.1.4.) can be run with the interface as well. The user in this case runs the first script (com-

mand: `python dependencies.py`), which installs all dependencies. It is nonetheless advised for a user to install the packages either manually or by `anaconda/miniconda`, as this first system is not bulletproof. The interface opens by commanding `python interlied_interface.py` which remains the last piece of code that needs to be inserted or reproduced manually. After that, the GUI's start menu (figure 2) offers the same three categories (figures 2 and 3), controlled by inserting data to the designated spaces or uploading the documents by pressing the button. All information that is obtained by this algorithm is automatically saved to the user's computer, except the plots, which can be saved manually when plotted.

(a) InterLied's Menu

(b) InterLied's Analysis Functions

Figure 2: InterLied GUI - Start Menu and Analysis

(a) InterLied's Visualisation Functions

(b) One of InterLied's Explore Functions

Figure 3: InterLied GUI - visualisation and Exploration

Chapter 4

Case Study: Slovenian 20th century Lieder

4.1 Introduction

The case study will examine the music patterns in lieder by three Slovenian composers, Slavko Osterc (1895–1941), Marij Kogoj (1892–1956) and Lucijan Marija Škerjanc (1900–1973). We must note that Slovenian lieder as well as the three composers were studied by many valuable contributions, delivered by Nataša Cigoj Krstulović [34], Gregor Pompe [35, 36, 37, 38, 39], Matjaž Barbo [40, 41, 42, 43] and Manica Špendal [44], Dragotin Cvetko [45, 46], Primož Kuret [47], Ivan Klemenčič [48, 49, 50], Katarina Bedina [51, 52] and Borut Loparnik [53]. The common message from the authors can be that although Slovenian music was inspired by the European trends, it is not to be neglected that these composers also streamed towards “Slovenian” uniqueness, at first connected to the “Slovenian” culture, and in later years to their own expression. The contributions above explored the opuses of the composers as well as lied structures, however, none of these further explored similarities and differences in music patterns. This research is thus aware of the findings and trying to further extend the topic by applying different sets of methodologies.

This chapter will first introduce some of the findings of the upper contributions,

throughout which I will try to bring the reader closer to the explored topic. It is necessary to understand the background in order to better comprehend the outcomes of the analyses. The “context” section will first expose the meaning of “lied” in broader context as well as in more “localised” sense and then connect these circumstances to the creative processes of the three composers.

Finally, the case study will explore the corpus by posing two general questions, first of which will undertake the role of melodic-rhythmic repetition, while the second will explore the connections between melodic and lyric patterns, explaining the similarities and differences between the musical expression of all three composers, Kogoj, Škerjanc and Osterc.

4.1.1 Lieder and Related Musicological Research

The term “lied”, although often simply translated as a vocal piece with accompaniment or “art song” has very complex and diverse meanings from language to language. Therefore, it is necessary to understand its past to apply it to the research. One of the most extensive contribution to lieder understanding was completed by James Parsons with his monograph *The Cambridge Companion to the Lied* in 2004 [54]. He talks about lied from historical musicological perspective, especially focusing on European and most precisely German traditions. Complimentary to this, Deborah Stein and Robert Spillman edited a publication called *Poetry into song* which in contrast focused on poetry behaviour and performance practice of the lied [55]. Both, and many other contributions can agree that the 20th century undoubtedly marked a turning point for this genre. As Parsons observes, German lied of the 18th century first embodied something, “natural” or “simple” for both performers and audience [54]. As the middle-higher social class continued to develop, so has the lied. First with Franz Schubert and then Robert Schumann, the lieder eventually moved from aristocratic courts to bourgeois saloons. Becoming a sort of a trend, now encapsulating the aesthetically and artistically “higher”, more “complex” content, the demands for compositions grow, becoming one of the biggest sources of income for composers. The form’s elasticity allowed both experienced and amateur composers

to express all of their knowledge in a relatively short piece, often performed to a more attentive audience. 20th century changed this relationship by moving the musical events to bigger venues, such as concert halls. From a vocal-piano piece performed to a smaller audience, the lieder in a way lost its way for a while, being dominated by orchestral and chamber pieces, the genres adjusted to accumulate large spaces. Although its meaning was shortly standing on unstable grounds, the lied continued to serve as experimental tool for composers, both compositional and performance-wise, while also, like many other arts, remained the mirror of the society. The latter is especially true for all of the nations, which were gradually building their national identity, utilising vocal music pieces to spread cultural ideas, language, and artistic value [56].

4.1.2 Slovenian 20th Century Lieder

Slovenian 19th century lied alongside other especially vocal genres served one of the foundations for national awakening movements. This extended well into the 20th century, however by then, the artists were already more motivated to pursue high art built on cultural and intellectual theories as well. As Gregor Pompe explains, there were two types of secession that separated 19th century from 20th century music, musically-aesthetic and musically sociological [35]. We must comprehend that until this point various Slovenian musicians could not afford good artistic education abroad and the one taught on Slovenian grounds was still in development. At the turn of the century, this vastly changes as more and more artists educate themselves abroad (e.g., at the prestigious today known as Czech, Austrian, German, French, or Italian institutions). Despite bringing the foreign knowledge back to their homeland, the swift changes were uncommon, as, in contrast with other firm traditional countries' arts and culture, the Slovenian "style" had yet to be established. Hence, the artists that had at the time considered themselves "avantgarde", unlike elsewhere, kept some rather conventional approaches (musical structure, style and or genre wise) upon which they slowly built their own, more refined style [56].

The key milestone in Slovenian music composition history was the year of 1927,

connected to return of Slavko Osterc from his studies in Prague, Škerjanc has reached the most radical compositional moment, while Kogoj drafted his opera *Črne maske* (*Black Masks*), an almost revolutionary music piece in Slovenian's music history. As all three composers, who remain the focus of these case studies, were progressing, so was the observed genre – lied. Lieder and other musical shapes gradually began to intake the foreign influences from all around the Europe, which were brought to their homeland by a new, younger generation of composers. The view on what a “national” art is changed as well. With the influence of expressionist tendencies, the composers not only relied on “peoples” heritage but also considered their individual internal streaming to be the expression of “the national”. This step inevitably moved the arts, in this case the music, from the romantic propensities of beaux arts or beautiful arts at all costs.

Kogoj, Škerjanc and Osterc sought to renovate the Slovenian soundscapes, however this did not mean that they agreed with each other's methods or had issues with older generation, then the authorities. Kogoj, the sharpest opponent to the “tradition” was continuously addressing the faults in the music sphere, which step by step pushed him to the edge of Slovenian music circle. Although he was very persistent, his gradual loss of will and health issues force him to make space for new, incredibly charismatic authority – Slavko Osterc. We must not mistake this personality as the continuation of “the old”, as his words toward the Slovenian music were just as sharp and critical. What separated him from Kogoj was, that he was able to assure himself a strong institutional support [56]. If Kogoj adapted the somewhat modernistic-expressionistic gestures, Osterc on the other hand believed in the objective, intellectually formulated and non-repetitive musical thoughts. The third of three, Škerjanc, who eventually, like Osterc, became one of the greatest musical authorities of their time, influenced by French impressionists, in contrast believed that the future of music belongs to subjective, harmonically inventive musical forms [56]. Surely, we must take into consideration the composers' development of style from their beginnings to the end of their career. When we interpret the results, we will require some knowledge on the role of lieder in each of their opuses, so let us swiftly observe their relation to the genre first.

Kogoj's career began by generally composing choral pieces. Although he has gone through several stages of music education (even attended some lessons with Arnold Schönberg in Vienna), his stubborn attitude towards the concept of institution prevented him to ever completing any formal education and was thus mostly self-taught [56]. He strongly opposed direct mimicking of any compositional style for the purpose of mimicking, but instead believed in the idea of expressing the inner self. Of course, this did not mean he invented his own style as his inner self has agreed with several bits and pieces, already established by his predecessors. His musical focus was melody and expanded harmony. His pieces were moving away from long romantic patterns, but instead incorporate a mosaic-like short musical thoughts or motifs. These were mainly built by smaller melodic intervals and were often repeated throughout the piece, however, they rarely exposed a firm harmonic relationship with any particular key. This was also true for the lieder, which were a part of his early, radical middle and late opuses [56]. Although he committed his life to music, he never stopped being fond of the other arts and literature as well, therefore, he paid great attention to not only the structure but also the content and style of the poetry used for each lied.

The style of Slavko **Osterc** was a firm believer in the saying “new is always better,” but did he actually create by this rule? In one of the journals of the time, he notes, “originality is an absolute prerequisite for any artistic form” [57]. But we can see from his corpus that he never really left the “traditional” traces behind. Especially form and harmony-wise, the latter of which in truth, did not play a vast role in his artistic processes. Instead of the vertical, Osterc focused on building interesting horizontal musical events [35]. In theory he detested the repetitions, but in practice, we can frequently encounter them in his corpus. He preferred building the melodic lines with smaller intervals, such as seconds and thirds, but he has not omitted larger jumps. Another parameter he was very fond of was rhythm, resulting in numerous meter changes within a single music piece.

Both Osterc and **Škerjanc** were aware that, despite their wish for radical change, there were a lot of musical genres that never fully came to life on Slovenian grounds,

thus they both felt the need to fill these holes. Škerjanc took a rather systematic approach to this and was moving from genre to genre, meaning the lieder generally appear in a very limited time of his creative path – in the beginning. Nonetheless, he left behind the most lieder of the three and has returned to them from time to time in his later years. In contrast to Kogoj’s or Osterc’s principles, Škerjanc almost never completely neglected the traditional harmony, seasoning it with colourful sound structures as his general influence were the impressionists. Consequently, for him, the harmony (at least when we talk about his early and late years) was the primary musical parameter. His melodic structures are rather recitative, as his principle was to paint the general atmosphere of the set poem with the piano [35]. While Škerjanc’s lieder remain to this day one of the most known and frequently performed Slovenian lieder, the closeness of his lieder with the “tradition” has in his time received many negative critics, especially by his “avantgarde” colleagues [56].

4.2 Dataset Introduction

This study includes 63 scores by three mentioned composers, Marij Kogoj, Lucijan Marija Škerjanc and Slavko Osterc (see full list in Appendix A). The scores were retrieved from the Music Collection of National University Library (Ljubljana, Slovenia). All scores were prints that I manually scanned and parsed through PhotoScore application. The results were far from perfect, especially in the case of old print processing. Then the mistakes were corrected and the available metadata information was added, both in Sibelius. From there, they were exported as musicXML files. The scores were re-checked in Musescore and separated into their individual folders, from where the material was ready to be analysed.

While more detailed analysis of some pieces was already made in the past [56], the goal of the following two case studies is to showcase some of the functionalities of InterLied. In order to do so, I will use it to answer two musicological questions regarding Slovenian Lieder.

4.3 Case study 1: The Role of Melodic-Rhythmic Repetition

The first question will observe the relationship between melodic and rhythmic pattern in each of the three composers' corpus (see full list of the examined scores in Appendix A). The general motivation here was determine the rhythmic-melodic dependency in composers' corpora. This was concluded by observing the top three melodic repetitions that have the same complementary rhythmic pattern, again per all selected scores in each of the composers' corpus. As we have seen in the introduction, not all composers had the same theoretical principles and preferences considering the usage of melodic and rhythmic music material, as well as have not had held the same posture towards repetitions of such material.

Before we consider the relationship between two of the most fundamental musical parameters, we will create a general overview of the approach and the analysis of both, melodic and rhythmic patterns, respectively.

I have started my analysis by selecting the same amount of scores (21 scores per composer) that were composed in the approximately same time period (mostly in 20s and 30s of the 20th century). I have inserted the scores into the InterLied's interval analysis and waited for the results, that were later parsed through the second, InterLied's pattern function. Both, interval and pattern outputs (now in csv format) have been grouped per composer (e.g., all outputs of one composer per function were now stored in a single csv file). All pre-selected scores combined per composers resulted in a similar length with Marij Kogoj having the longest list of intervals (1902), followed by Osterc (1746) and lastly by Škerjanc (1695). Here, we must note that Osterc in fact had the shortest compositions, but many of Škerjanc's works have been removed to balance out the data, thus resulting in unintentionally selecting seemingly shorter pieces. Also, interval length does not mean the actual length of the composition as we must, in addition, take into account the distribution frequency and duration of these intervals. Nonetheless, merged files have then allowed me to observe composer's corpus as a whole instead of analysing

each score separately. The function that I found most useful for this study, was the visualisation of ten most frequent values, through which I explored the most frequently used intervals, melodic and rhythmic patterns in the three sub-corpora. For the purpose of additionally inspecting the meter changes, I adapted this function to retrieve the relevant results. In the final instance, most frequent melodic patterns were explored by InterLied's explore function.

Starting with the **melodic** material of **Marij Kogoj**, it can be seen from the analysis (figures 4 and 5) that he used the least repetitions of the same pattern in his compositions, as the usage of each, when we consider all three composers, is the most evenly distributed among the most common patterns and intervals. As we have pointed out in the introduction, it was unlike him to repeat large masses of patterns, thus the largest and smallest repeated pattern in the top 10 category consists of only 2 intervals. If we observe all of the repeated patterns, the longest consists of 9 intervals, however this only appears in three out of twenty lieder (*Nad mestom belim*, *Otožnost*, and *Stopil sem na tihe njive*). The largest jump in these patterns is a minor third up, thus large jumps are more of an exceptional events than a repeated rule in pattern work. When we speak about the latter, despite his musical expression remained anchored in the late-romantic chromatic and these were the building blocks of most of his repeated melodic patterns, Kogoj was no stranger to larger intervals (>M3) as they appear in his corpus 201 times. Because we have observed that these do not play a large role in his repeated pattern work, we could assume the larger jumps served as a tool for accenting certain musical or lyrical spots, to separate them from the "usual". The patterns often consist of a sequence of two of the same interval (e.g. P_1, P_1; M-2, M-2, etc.) or start by a unison and another interval (commonly minor or major second). The unison is a very commonly used interval in his work, however so are minor and major seconds. Due to this somewhat even distribution, Kogoj's compositional style appears as the least recitative of all three.

of 8 duration values, all of which being eighth notes. The longest duration in the most common rhythmic pattern is a half note, while the shortest is the eighth note. Rhythmic patterns are in general more or less composed of the same values, with one or two being mixed. We can observe some syncopated rhythmic sequences, but these are not very frequent. Here, we can already notice that rhythm did not play the most important role as there is little rhythmic variety.

Figure 6: Top 10 duration values in lieder by Marij Kogoj

When we consider the **melodic-rhythmic** patterns in **Kogoj's** corpus, it can be seen that some patterns do occur in the exact same form, both melodically and rhythmically. For the purpose of confirming this, top three melodic patterns will be observed with their complementary rhythmic structures. The most frequent pattern is a repeated unison (e.g., P_1, P_1) to which we can find two repeated complementary rhythmic patterns. First is four times repeated eighth. This one can be found twice in lied *Gazela* and four times in *Stopil sem na tihe njive*. The second one is a pattern of two eighth notes followed by two quarter notes, also present in lied *Stopil sem na tihe njive* (two times). The rest of the melodic-rhythmic combinations for this pattern only appear once per score. The second, almost equivalently frequent pattern of two descending major seconds (M-2, M-2), which occurs in separate measures of lieder *Sprehod v zimi* (twice) and *Vrnitev* (twice). A second most frequent integral rhythmic pattern is a sequence of four quarter notes, which appears four times in *Rasla je roža*. The rest of the melodic patterns only occur once per

certain rhythmic structure in each score. Lastly, we have a pair of descending major second followed by a unison. This pattern corresponds with four eighth notes and occurs in *Otožnost* (two times). As the results indicate, the composer did to some extent think of a melodic-rhythmic structures as one, however, it is not obligatory for the two to appear in the exact same form. Since his most commonly used patterns of any kind seldom appear longer than two intervals, we can confirm that he has indeed focused more on the melodic than rhythmic parameter, as well as to major extent left the tradition of long repeated rhythmically-melodic lines.

In **melodic structure** of **Lucijan Marija Škerjanc** lieder (figures 7 and 8), we immediately notice a strong focus on recitative part, seeing that both unison interval and pattern composed of unison both confidently take the first position in top ten visualisation. A unison is also a very frequent starting point of a pattern, as it appears on the first position in 7 out of 10 patterns. Like Kogoj, Škerjanc also considered chromatic patterns to be one of the general building blocks of his melodic structures. We can observe, that for him, large jumps ($>M3$) do not take a major role in frequent patterns, however, do appear very often (202 times) as a single interval. The largest interval that is listed among the ten most popular is descending perfect fifth (P-5), which occurs in his corpus 64 times. The largest pattern jump, on the other hand, is a ascending major third (M+3).

Figure 7: Top 10 interval values in lieder by Lucijan M. Škerjanc

Figure 8: Top 10 melodic pattern values in lieder by Lucijan M. Škerjanc

The **rhythmic patterns** in Škerjanc's collection are mostly represented by a sequence of four eighth notes (figure 9), followed largely behind by four quarter notes and then again by six eighth notes. In contrast to Kogoj's lieder, these have more variety to them, being composed of mixed values, such as quarter and eighth notes, sometimes also half notes, and less frequently with a dotted quarter note. Here, we can also find some but not a lot of syncopated rhythmic patterns. The longest rhythmic pattern consists of 6 rhythm values.

The most popular melodic pattern of Škerjanc, having much more repetitions than any of Kogoj's patterns, a sequence of two unisons, is in contrast to the first **melodic-rhythmic** pattern analysis commonly repeated in the exactly the same melodic-rhythmic structure. We can see that a sequence of interdependent four quarter notes appears twice in *Jesenska pesem*, a sequence of a quarter note, two half notes and again quarter note (1.0, 2.0, 2.0, 1.0) occurs two times in *Pesem ob ločitvi*, then again a sequence of three quarter notes, followed by a dotted eighth note makes two appearances in *Pesem*. We can observe multiple repetitions of the melodic pattern with correlative rhythmic values also in *V Poldnevu* (three times), *Aleja sniva* (more than 5 repetitions) and *Samotno pirovanje* (numerous repetitions). We could probably find some more, but for the purpose of this research, let us move on to the second most popular pattern, which is, like in Kogoj's corpus,

Figure 9: Top 10 duration values in lieder by Lucijan M. Škerjanc

a sequence of two descending major seconds. It is largely present as a sequence of four eighth notes, especially in *Aleja sniva* and *Sonet*), but also as a sequence of four quarter notes, found in *Pesem ob ločitvi*, *Sonet* and *V tujini*, the second of which introduces another reciprocal rhythmic structure twice, which is a quarter note, followed by three eighth notes. Equally as often, a melodic pattern of unison and ascending major second occurs. This pattern is accompanied by three rhythmic variants, first of which being four consecutive quarter notes, found twice in *Pesem ob ločitvi*. Second rhythmic form is composed of a quarter and half note, followed by two more quarter notes, and can also be found in *Pesem ob ločitvi*. The last, dotted quarter note, followed by three eighth notes, can be found twice in lied *V tujino*. Opposed to Kogoj, Škerjanc put more focus on connecting the two parameters and considered them as a whole in numerous compositions.

The last of the three, **Slavko Osterc** also considered recitative **melodic patterns** (figures 10 and 11) as a crucial ingredient in his compositions. As it can be monitored from the analysis, both intervals and patterns indicate a clear commitment towards building his melodic structures with unison. Like all three, the next in line are

minor and major seconds, thus chromatic melodic movements were common in his lieder as well. The largest jumps, like in Kogoj's instance, do not exceed a major second in patterns and perfect fifth among intervals. The latter is actually the only high jump among any top ten melodic instances, thus it is highly unlikely he considered melodic diversity as a necessity. In his works, we find the most repeated longest melodic pattern, however this does not suggest that Osterc was the most comfortable supporter of long pattern repetitions among the three. On the contrary, the observed sequence, built completely out of unisons only re-confirms his distance towards highly contrasting melodies.

Figure 10: Top 10 interval values in lieder by Slavko Osterc

Figure 11: Top 10 melodic pattern values in lieder by Slavko Osterc

When it comes to **Osterc** and **rhythmic patterns** (figure 12), there are many eighth note sequences that, extend up to eight values. The top ten patterns are the most repeated patterns among the three composer, as even the least repeated one appears 46 times. We can observe that while the largest value does not surpass the length of a quarter note, he was not opposed to using the smallest values among all observed, utilising sixteenth notes. Besides long sequences of eighth notes and one sequence of four quarter note values and one of four sixteenth note values, we can also witness a lot of mixed-value patterns. This leads us to believe that Osterc, as introduced in the introduction section, valued rhythmic structures considerably more than he did the melodic variety.

Figure 12: Top 10 duration values in lieder by Slavko Osterc

If we, in the end, explore the **melodic-rhythmic patterns** in compositions by **Slavko Osterc**, there is a lot of repetitions, however most of these are connected to the nature of recitative, speech-like parts. If we explore the most frequent pattern, a repeated unison, one example is four consecutive quarter notes in *Biba leze* (repetitions occur between measures 19 and 30), and another *Jurij in belouška* (repetitions occur two times). Similar goes for complementary quarter note sequence, which occurs in lieder *Na poljani* and *Jurij in belouška*. The latter includes a lot of repetitions with a variety of rhythmic patterns. We can also find correspondence

between this melodic pattern and different repeated rhythms in *Dere sen jas mali bija*, *Slavec*, *Zvečer* and *Zvezde žarijo*. Next observed pattern, a descending major second followed by an unison, can be found three times in *Na poljani* and two times in *Jurij in belouška* as a sequence of two quarter notes, followed by two eighth notes. It can also occur in repeated correspondence with eighth note, followed by a dotted quarter note, quarter note and another eighth note in *Bolne rože*. This melodic pattern can again be found with repeated rhythmic structure in *Dere sen jas mali bija*, *Štiri belokranjske*, *Slavec*, *Za materjo* and *Zvečer*. As we further explore his corpus, we admittedly find more examples of repeated melodic-rhythmic patterns in a great deal of his compositions, which indicates that he did not neglect a melodic-rhythmic structure as a whole and a worthy compositional constituent. Here, we can detect the discrepancies between Osterc, the theoretician and Osterc, the composer.

It is clear that all three composers shared some of the compositional approaches, but to comment on rhythmic variety, it is important, that we also take into account the **meter changes** that occur in their compositions (figures 13-15). With the meter changing, it is unlikely that the rhythm keeps the exact same values, thus should we translate all of the rhythmic values of melodic lines, we may be able to search for some more connections between correspondent melodic-rhythmic patterns. As we can see from the figures 13, 14 and 15 below ("yes" = meter changes at least once, "no" = there is no meter change), all three were very keen on changing the meter in their compositions, least of all Škerjanc.

Figure 13: Meter changes in Kogoj's lieder

Figure 14: Meter changes in Škerjanc's lieder

Figure 15: Meter changes in Osterc's lieder

To add to this observation, I included below the three figures that indicate the most popular choices of meters per composition. It is noticeable that Kogoj (figure 16) used more than two mixed meters in a single compositions in almost half of his

observed works (9 times), while Škerjanc (figure 17) only chose to do so in four and Osterc (figure 18) in three. It is interesting that Osterc uses one of the most “basic” meters (4/4) only in three of his compositions (only once as a single meter), Kogoj applied this meter to 13 of his lieder, while Škerjanc used it in the most of his lieder (15, to be exact). There is no doubt that more can be observed here. However, as the general question proposed the observation of melodic-rhythmic patterns, the main take-home message from this addition is, to stress one of the reasons for not finding more complementary rhythmic and melodic pattern, is a trend of very frequent time signature change. Nonetheless, I believe, this would not make any major changes to the very telling findings above. This statement is confirmed by looking at the only repeated melodic-rhythmic patterns in Kogoj’s corpus, among which (with one exception) all of the scores that have a trace of such repetitions actually have multiple meters already, while the rest of the scores that were composed upon a single meter do not belong to the observed most relevant repetitions.

Figure 16: All 20 meter combinations in lieder by Marij Kogoj

Figure 17: All 20 meter combinations in lieder by Lucijan Marija Škerjanc

Figure 18: All 20 meter combinations in lieder by Slavko Osterc

4.2.1 Conclusion

This case study pays attention to the corpora built by 63 compositions by three Slovenian composers. The theoretical frame, set by the studies of many established musicologists, was observed through the prism of computational music pattern analysis. An abbreviated study illustrated the composers' relationship with repeated melodic-rhythmic patterns and also their posture towards each parameter separately.

It can be noted, that while Slavko Osterc and Lucijan Marija Škerjanc more apparently utilise the repeated unison patterns and oftentimes repeat both rhythmic and melodic structure within a single score, Marij Kogoj uses his musical resources considerably more in moderation and is merely a devotee to a literal melodic-rhythmic repetitions. Škerjanc and Kogoj are more involved in the melody building, while Osterc's ambitions rather focus on a rhythmic diversity. None of the three composers uses large jumps as a part of the common patterns often, least of all Osterc. The three do not neglect the late-romantic chromatics, but none considered this parameter as their first concern. The study added a quick overview of the meter changes in the compositions and raised an important issue of taking other parameters into consideration while making conclusions. We could also argue our findings through minor/major key changes, length, ornamentation etc. However, from observation, it is unlikely that the results obtained would require a vastly different interpretation.

4.4 Case study 2: Melody Versus Lyric

The second case study explores the possible connections between lyric word semantics and elements connected to the melody (and harmony). This study uses the same corpora as case study 1, but in addition to the interval analysis functions, now also includes InterLied's lyric analysis function. The outputs of both are further explored through visualisation algorithms, in particular the two that directly consider the connection between different types of musical and metadata elements and lyric tokens. First, I observed the relationship between most common intervals and lyric tokens. I also used lyric analysis output to consider the lyric text as a whole and its connection to computationally predicted score key, focusing on major/minor type of scale instead of considering each separately. Here, we must always be aware that keys are a tricky topic. First of all, they are retrieved computationally. Second of all, the 20th century compositions (as it was explained in the corpus introduction) rarely clearly fixate on a single key, if any, thus the more composer is known to be dedicated to the "traditional" key definition, the more accurate and relevant the results are and vice versa. In even the most "key-reliable" compositions, modula-

tions can appear, therefore, if we are interested in this matter in detail, one should first split the parts of modulation or use algorithms that provide a more reliable key detection. Another issue that presented itself was word processing. As this may be more effective with some of the other languages that can easily go through another phase of natural language processing - lemmatization (to reduce a given word to its root word), this was found too difficult to achieve with the included language - Slovenian. Therefore, each form of a noun, verb etc. was considered as a separate, “stand-alone” word, resulting in more scattered, less graspable results. Should one be interested in analysing a smaller portion of scores (or a single score), it is possible to achieve this manually. However, for a “big data” analyses, it is advised to consult the NLP specialists. Thus, the less significant results found related to the words or topic and interval relationship may be closely connected to the described issue.

4.3.1 Lyric Tokens and Minor vs Major Key Relationship

Let us begin by introducing the data that was used for the **lyric token and key** analysis and the obtained results, composer by composer. I will begin this section with **Marij Kogoj** (figures 19 and 20). I have analysed 21 of his scores that were composed in 15 different keys. All of the lyric observed included 3742 tokenized words. His corpus is considered to be the least concentrated on a firm, single key, therefore the results here have the least weight. Nonetheless, we can observe, from the figure below, that the two most frequent words in the corpus that presumably belong to a minor scaled score are actually “tears” (*solze*). Among the top 10 we can also find “jesus” (*jezus*) and see there are two repetitions of “rock” (*kamen*), “to look” (*pogledala* or *pogledati*), “night” (*noč*), “hope” (*nade* or *nada*), “to rip” (*raztrgala* or *raztrgati*), “old man” (*starec*), “flowers” (*rožic[e]*) and “fields” (*polja*). Opposed to minor scale, major scale category has a rather less obvious emphasis. The distribution is much more equal and includes various expressions with different types of meanings, of different “semantic” categories. We can thus observe “thirsty” (*žejna*), “sun” (*sonce*), “silent” (*tih*), “got up” (*vstal*), “night” (*noč*), “to rest / to sleep” (*dremlje* or *dremati*), “heavy” (*težek*), “cloudy” (*oblačen*), “day” (*dan*), “to believe” (*verovala* or *verovati*). Even though minor does seem to attract a certain

“topic” to it, I believe the ambivalence of “key” of Kogoj’s composition does not give this type of analysis enough credibility. As we must note that, again, the more certainty there is about the “key” the more this type of analysis thrives.

Figure 19: Kogoj: Most frequent lyric tokens in major keys

Figure 20: Kogoj: Most frequent lyric tokens in minor keys

I am now moving on to the corpus of **Lucijan Marija Škerjanc** (figures 21 and 22), where there were also 21 scores selected. These were composed in 14 different keys and included precisely 4621 words, which is the largest amount of lyric word tokens among the three composers. The “major” key again, as well as in Kogoj’s corpus,

does not offer a firm conclusion, while “minor” key words are generally connected calmer, darker, melancholic topics, such as “clouds” (*oblaki*), “far away” (*daleč*), “black” (*črni*) and “night” (*noč*). There are some connections, but I would again say that the results are inconclusive.

Figure 21: Škerjanc: Most frequent lyric tokens in major keys

Figure 22: Škerjanc: Most frequent lyric tokens in minor keys

Last but not least, I analysed 21 scores by **Slavko Osterc** (figures 23 and 24), which were composed in 10 different keys and include 4140 word tokens. Here, as slightly expected, we see the most conclusive results. We can clearly observe that the most frequent words include playfulness (such as playful expressions *tralala* and *ač*, light (such as “stars” (*zvezde*)) and nature/temporal categories (such as “blooming” (*vzcvetele* or *vzcveteti*), “flowers” (*rože*), “day” (*dan*) and so on). On the other hand, we have a minor scale category, to which the most common word “evening” (*večer*) appears together of four times. Some others appear, such as “night” (*noč*) and “day”

(*dan*), but as they only appear two times, they lose their relevancy on a larger scale. Among all three composers, we could say Osterc did, to some extent at least, choose his keys according to the chosen lyric topic.

Figure 23: Osterc: Most frequent lyric tokens in major keys

Figure 24: Osterc: Most frequent lyric tokens in minor keys

4.3.2 Lyric Tokens and Intervals Relationship

In the first case study, we observed the most frequent patterns and intervals and their relation to the rhythm. In this section, we will consider exactly those intervals in relation to lyric tokens. The acquired results of this experiment were scattered among numerous plots (e.g., one per interval per composer), hence, the results will be descriptive and will not include visualisations.

In **Kogoj's** corpus, we can see an increased appearance of words, like “night” (*noč*), “cloudy” (*oblačen*) and “difficult” (*težek*) connected to minor second and minor third.

However, some (less frequently) also appear with perfect fifth, where the most common word is “flowers” (*rožic* or *rožice*). The latter appears with the perfect fourth as well. We do see some traces of connections between the melody and topic, but the results here are inconclusive. In **Škerjanc’s** lieder it can be noticed, that descending perfect fifth is closely related to the word “home” (*doma* or *dom*), while it also appears with the words “white” (*belo*), “fertile” (*rodnih* or *rodno*), and “better” (*boljšega* or *boljši*), but these appear much less frequently as “home”. The rather lighter topics are also related to the ascending perfect fourth, such as “white” (*beli*), “brighter” (*svetlejša*), “lovely” (*prekrasna*), and “heart” (*srca* or *srce*), but yet again, these are not very frequent. On the other hand we have an ascending minor second, which is connected to a variety of topics and does not show a dedication to a single theme. Once again it may be **Osterc**, whose lieder alludes the most connections between the two elements, connecting the “darker”, “less cheerful” topics to minor intervals and seconds. The word “army” (*vojska*) appears with minor and major seconds (ascending and descending), as well as with minor third. The word “evening” (*večer*) appears with a descending minor second (4 times), ascending minor second (6 times), and ascending major second (4 times), while “stars” and “little stars” (*zvezde*, *zvezdice*) appear in descending minor third (together 5 times). The word dead (*mrtvo*, *mrtve*) is closely connected to descending minor third and ascending major second. The top two words related to the latter are, on the other hand, “sing” (*poje*) and a “song” (*pesem*).

4.3.3 Conclusion

The second case study approached the issue of relationships between musical (key and interval) elements and lyric semantics (word tokens). The study concluded that the most clear relationship between the observed components can be seen in lieder by Slavko Osterc, who connects the major keys and larger intervals to slightly lighter topics than he does with the minor keys and intervals. The results in general could not draw substantial conclusions. This case study therefore also highlights the limitations of working with lyric - a topic more at home in the natural language processing department. The short example raised the need for further utilisation of

NLP approaches, among which a very useful next step would be to add a convincing lemmatization and topic modeling tools for each of the offered languages. The latter issue was raised especially with the language in question - Slovenian, which, for now, with its specifics requires a lot of manual “adjustments.” Another issue was pointed out - an issue that was presented in the introductory section of both, this thesis and this chapter - the importance of knowing the corpus one is researching well enough to expect which tools would help one achieve the most relevant results. Since we have learned in the lieder introduction section that these composers, as well as 20th century music in general, was often expanding their branches from the “traditional” harmonic structures, any of the offered key analyses (both, computational and manual) do not provide the most efficient outcome if done “per score” or “per corpus”, but would instead have to be done “per smaller part(s) in a score.” To sum up, the more the corpus’ structure corresponds with the analytical techniques and the more we understand the methods of these techniques, the more a researcher can benefit from the results.

Chapter 5

Discussion

5.1 Discussion

This thesis explored an issue of interdisciplinarity in computational music research. While the interdisciplinarity between IT and digital humanities remains crucial for the further, efficient development of both fields, we have observed that in doing so, both, humanities and information technologies must be able to communicate their findings with one another in order to cooperate.

InterLied addressed this issue and proposed a solution, which was mainly projected through the matter of accessibility. This project focused on creating a set of open source tools for music analysis and data extraction, accessible to users of different computational ability levels. Since musicology is an essential aspect of the research I have carried out, I will first focus on the results from this point of view. Hence, the following sections will dissect the advantages, limitations and future possibilities of the project will build arguments based in musicology.

It should be noted that the raw inputs and outputs are not sufficient for this apparatus to be fully useful for any concise result interpretation. InterLied was not built with the purpose to draw final conclusions from the data, so the user should always understand the content they are analysing and have a clear idea of why they are utilising these tools.

Second, we must be aware of the precise preparation of scores. InterLied was designed and first tried on a total of 63 scores large corpus by three Slovenian composers (e.g., three composers from the same country and era). The scores were transcribed with Sibelius and were then converted to musicXML. Some errors occurred with this conversion and had to be dealt with manually (e.g., mistaking articulation mark for lyrics or skipping the lyric on a note etc.). When these were successfully processed, the next step was to collect random scores and evaluate algorithms' flexibility. Out of 18 non-adapted musicXML song scores, randomly selected from the MuseScore repository, 15 were passable. Although fully and fluently parsed, some information of certain scores was missing (e.g., lyricist, composer or had title and composer combined etc.). What I observed from the process was that, we must pay special attention to manually checking the scores, even after they are processed through the InterLied code, as some additional issues could be noticed then. The researcher must not solely rely on the algorithm, as wrongly applied information to the score causes the functions to skip or return the wrong information. Nonetheless, it was observed that the algorithm can easily parse any scores and not only the corpus that the functions were developed on. This leads to the advantage of having CSV format as an output confirmed itself to be very useful for the users with less computational experience. It forms a very telling format, which allows the individual to observe each step of the data processing, can directly interact with the possible errors and easily corrects them without interfering with the algorithms.

Third, the system is very flexible as it is able to process different types of scores (e.g. arias, lieder from different eras, of different languages, by different composers or even different single voiced genres) do not disturb the fluidity of the algorithm, as long as the score is translated to musicXML format in Common Western Music Notation (CMWN) and vocal or single voice part is stored in first part (e.g., part [0]). The latter can be easily adapted as well, even by computational beginners. The only hiccup we have met with was the lyric processing when applying different languages. As nltk library allows the user to choose among various languages when removing the stopwords, however a user can, for now, only use one language at the time, thus if their corpus is multilingual, a researcher must split it in groups and

process each group separately.

Fourth, the n-gram method for retrieving data offers a very understandable approach for a humanities researcher and is very flexible while trying to make minor changes, however as we have seen in the State Of the Art chapter, many more advanced approaches can be met in this field of research. What is the largest disadvantage of InterLied, is the literate translation of patterns. For example, the patterns do not always appear exactly the same (added ornamentation, leaving out a tone, etc.), but can be still perceived by the human ear as “identical”. InterLied cannot automatically adapt to this matter, while some other approaches have already begun with resolving this issue. Applying these algorithms, that frequently use very complex computational approaches, however, inevitably causes issues for a non-computational researcher to understand and utilise the code.

What presented itself as a larger issue during this particular research was applying other the NLP methods to lyrics of the lieder. Although the NLP and other text analysis approaches tend to be more attentive or rather more inclusive to the humanities, the language itself presents a large issue. The ADL methods and most similar algorithms are trained on the specific type of data and can be much less adaptive, as all languages have their own characteristics. To complete or utilize pre-composed NLP algorithms, one must therefore be either very skilled in building or adapting these methods or must be lucky enough to have had the extensive research already done in their language of interest. If we take the lieder that will be observed in the case studies, the characteristics of it had not allowed this project to further focus on this matter in order to assure precise methods. The lyrics do not always share the same language features, being mostly in Slovenian but also French and German, which prevents us from efficiently train the data. Another barrier is the length of the texts, as most of the lieder remain very short with no repetitions, thus provide rather concise texts. These texts are consequently too complex for this research to efficiently execute appropriate topic modeling. With this, we are moving to the future possibilities section.

5.1.1 Future work

As this research topic is far from being done with its progress, I believe there is a lot of room for advancement. That is, on music pattern analysis, NLP, and also accessibility and application level.

First, music patterns can be observed from numerous angles and rarely possess a firm definition, let alone are self-sufficient. While InterLied's algorithms do assure more flexibility and allow for further limitless inclusion of the desired parameters, the scientific questions humanities pose in their research can extend well beyond the algorithms' capabilities. Hence, these types of algorithmic packages need constant improvements and must assure collaboration between different scholars to be able to adapt to more unique situations. On the positive note, this project not only encourages these collaborations, but also aspires to inform these scholars on how to adapt the models to their needs, and thus tries to ensure more efficient and rapid process of improvement. This project will extend its roots in collaboration with Algomus lab, where we will first explore the possibilities of more accurate melodic, but most importantly also harmonic indexing. The tools will remain open source and will always provide a "user support system" for music theorists, musicologists and other (humanities) researchers.

As mentioned, InterLied slightly touches the field of NLP, however what a person does with the pre-processed text is up to them. For future work, I would like to include some of these options, such as efficient topic modeling, word embedding or some other methods of lexical semantics and implement them to the GUI as well. This would, however, require another interdisciplinary collaboration - the one between digital musicologists and digital linguists.

Another, for my case the most important improvement should be done on the accessibility and application level. This project deems to assure the user to be involved with the system and contributes to it, however, for this to be efficient, InterLied should provide more tutorials on basic matters. Secondly, the GUI should eventually grow into a web interface which would be able to connect not only individual

users' databases but especially the digital databases of various archives. This could represent itself as a solution for more efficient work with musical data and exploration. The latter would perhaps encourage a higher frequency of archival use, not only among researchers, but also among wider public. Visualisation of data could provide a better understanding of the raw musical information among musicians, music enthusiasts, university and high-school professors and students, etc.

Current limitations should be instead thought of as future challenges and while this thesis is concluded, the chapter of InterLied has not yet come to an end. To end with Cook's words, "All the potential for a major disciplinary advance in musicology is there, but we've got to put in place the conditions to make it actually happen. Otherwise we could be standing at this moment of opportunity for a long time to come" [58].

5.2 Conclusion

This master thesis explored the computational music analyses principles, generally connected to music patterns. It acknowledged the existing contributions which it exposes the issue of the accessibility of these methods to the music researchers without prior programming knowledge.

The musicologically-inspired project of this thesis, called InterLied, was inspired by this "fault" and introduced a set of easily adaptable tools for music analysis, accessible both through python scripts (and notebook) and GUI. The methods included in InterLied's package were primarily built on vocal lines of Slovenian lieder, however, they can be used on a variety of different single-voiced music parts. Analysed melodic and rhythmic information is accompanied by metadata and other musical information, such as key prediction and meter diversity. The methodology that concerns the computational data collection derives from music21, data science, and NLP.

The first of three algorithm categories analyses the score through melodic intervals (and complementary data), melodic interval patterns (and complementary data) and

tokenized lyric (and complementary data). The first converts the music intervals to text out of which, with the method of n-grams, music patterns are retrieved. The last of three analytical functions offers to process lyric and by tokenization prepares it for further NLP analyses in all languages otherwise available through nltk package [29]. After the data is prepared or analysed, InterLied enables the user to visualise or further explore their data through variety of functions (from midi representation, to different plots, search functions etc.). All functions are easily adapted to the researcher's needs with very little computational knowledge. In addition, the InterLied's repository¹ provides a detailed description of each of the included functions, which can, in abbreviated form, also be found in its notebook. The repository also offers GUI, which created to encourage the usage of digital tools among not computationally skilled humanities researchers and was inspired by many relevant projects, such as The Baudelaire Project and Unlocking Musicology. It can execute all analyses and visualises obtained data. It includes several feasible search options with direct data interaction, such as midi and score representation of the musical data, plots, statistical information and so on.

The thesis evaluates and demonstrates the InterLied's tools through two case studies, both related to Slovenian 20th century lieder, more precisely the lieder by Marij Kogoj, Lucijan Marija Škerjanc and Slavko Osterc. The chapter is dedicated to an introduction of the corpus and a comparative computational analysis of 63 scores. First of the two case studies examines the role of rhythmic and melodic components in each of the composers' corpus, while the second observes the relationships between lyric words and melodic elements.

Finally, the project provokes a discussion about the connections between computational and musicological (or, if you want, humanities in general) expertise. It suggest a series of possible advancements for both, the project in question, but also the collaborations in the field of computational music research.

¹<https://github.com/vnborsan/interlied>

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Appendix A

Dataset List

A.1 Marij Kogoj

1. "Ah, ne verjemi"
2. "Če sončna se razpenjajo vam pota"
3. "Drevo"
4. "Gazela"
5. "Istrski motiv"
6. "Jaz se te bom spomnila"
7. "Letski motiv"
8. "Na trgu"
9. "Nad mestom belim"
10. "Otožnost"
11. "Predanost"
12. "Rasla je roža"
13. "Res, če me ne maraš"
14. "Sprehod v zimi"
15. "Starec knjim"
16. "Stopil sem na tihe njive"
17. "Večnemu Bogu"
18. "Vrnitev"
19. "Za god"
20. "Zanka"
21. "Zvečer"

A.2 Lucijan Marija Škerjanc

1. "Aleja sniva"
2. "Baltazarjeva pesem"
3. "Beli oblaki"
4. "Hrepenenje"
5. "Jesenska pesem"
6. "Jesenski dan"
7. "Pahljača"
8. "Pesem"
9. "Pesem ob ločitvi"
10. "Pisma I."
11. "Počitek pod goro"
12. "Pomlad"
13. "Pomladne noči"
14. "Pred ogledalom"
15. "Samotno pirovanje"
16. "Sonet"
17. "V poldnevu"
18. "V tujino ..."
19. "Večer soparen bo ..."
20. "Večerna impresija"
21. "Vizija"

A.3 Slavko Osterc

1. "Ančka bančka"
2. "Biba leze"
3. "Bolne rože"
4. "Dere sen jas mali bija"
5. "Štiri belokranjske (I. - II.)"
6. "Štiri belokranjske (III. - IV.)"
7. "Japonski motiv"
8. "Jurij in belouška"
9. "Jurjevanje"
10. "Na poljani"
11. "Na trojki"
12. "Ni te na vrtu več"
13. "Pesem o devici Peregrini"
14. "Slavec"
15. "Sonce v zavesah"
16. "Tri pesmi"

17. "Uspavančica"

20. "Zvečer"

18. "Vrata"

19. "Za materjo"

21. "Zvezde žarijo"